

Implementing Single Shot Detector (SSD) for Object Detection in Advertisement Web Application for Easy Search

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Abstract— The goal of Machine Learning technology in this project, named Ad-Sol (solution for advertisement), is to implement the Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) algorithm for object detection in uploaded image files. The proposed solution aims to identify and localize objects within the uploaded images in real-time, without the need for a separate region proposal step. The SSD algorithm, which is a deep learning-based model, will be utilized to detect various objects in the images based on their object names.

Once the objects are detected, the system will implement a searching mechanism to make it easy to search for objects based on their names within the Ad-Sol project. This searching functionality will facilitate users in quickly locating objects of interest within the uploaded images and improve the overall user experience.

Keywords— Object detection, Single Shot MultiBox Detector, Image analysis, Real-time, Object localization

I. INTRODUCTION

Advertising has been an essential part of business operations for many years. In today's digital age, the process of advertising has become more complex, with various platforms and mediums available. However, with the rise of artificial intelligence and machine learning, there is an opportunity to streamline the advertising process and make it more efficient. This seminar paper will focus on Ad-Sol, an innovative web application that aims to simplify the advertising process for businesses and individuals. Ad-Sol provides an easy-to-use platform for advertisers to upload their ads. At the time of uploading, the application's machine learning algorithm detects the objects in the image and saves them to the database. This feature not only saves time but also provides a more straightforward search process for users.

The purpose of this seminar paper is to explore the functionality of Ad-Sol in detail. We will examine its design and development process, highlighting the unique features that make it stand out from other advertising platforms. Additionally, we will analyse the benefits that Ad-Sol offers to its users, including its efficiency, simplicity, and accuracy. This seminar paper will provide valuable insights into the

field of advertising and how machine learning can be utilized to simplify complex processes..

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Object detection is a fundamental computer vision task with wide-ranging applications, including autonomous vehicles, robotics, and surveillance. Among the many object detection methods that have been proposed, single shot detection (SSD) is a popular approach that has been shown to achieve high accuracy in real-time object detection.

A literature review of SSD image detection reveals several key findings. First, SSD is a deep learning-based approach that uses a convolutional neural network (CNN) to predict the class and location of objects in an image. The network is trained using a combination of localization and classification loss functions, which allow it to learn to accurately detect objects of varying sizes and shapes.

III. EASE OF USE

A. SSD object detection in image

Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) is a computer vision algorithm used for object detection in images. It is a deep learning-based method that uses convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to identify the location and class of objects in an image. SSD divides the image into a set of predefined boxes and applies a series of convolutional layers to extract features from each box. The algorithm then predicts the presence and class of an object in each box based on these features. Finally, it uses a technique called non-maximum suppression to eliminate duplicate detections and return the final set of detected objects in the image

IV. SINGLE SHOT DETECTOR-SSD

Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) algorithm for object detection in uploaded image files. The proposed solution aims to identify and localize objects within the uploaded images in real-time, without the need for a separate region proposal step. The SSD algorithm, which is a deep learning-based model, will be utilized to detect various objects in the images based on their object names.

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● Data and model

The pre-trained MobileNetSSD model and the corresponding prototxt file used by the code for object detection. The MobileNetSSD model is a deep neural network that is trained on a large dataset of images to detect various objects, while the prototxt file specifies the architecture of the model. The code reads in these files to perform object detection on the input image.

The MobileNetSSD model used in the code is one such deep learning model. It is a variant of the MobileNet model that has been optimized for real-time object detection on mobile devices and embedded systems.

● Image Processing.

Once the image is received by the Flask application through the POST request, it is read as binary data using `'request.files['image'].read()'`. This binary data is then converted into a NumPy array using the `'np.frombuffer()'` function, which creates a one-dimensional array from the binary data.

The NumPy array is then decoded into an image using the `'cv2.imdecode()'` function, which takes the NumPy array and a flag that specifies how the image should be decoded. In this case, `'cv2.IMREAD_COLOR'` is used to decode the image as a 3-channel color image.

Next, the image is resized to a fixed size of 300x300 pixels using the `'cv2.resize()'` function. The reason for resizing the image is that the MobileNetSSD model expects inputs of this specific size.

The resized image is then processed using the `'cv2.dnn.blobFromImage()'` function, which prepares the image for input into the neural network. This function performs mean subtraction, scaling, and channel swapping on the input image, and returns a blob which is then fed as input to the MobileNetSSD model. Overall, the image processing part of the code takes care of converting the binary image data into a format that can be input into the MobileNetSSD model for object detection..

● Object detection.

Object Detection is the process of detecting and localizing objects in an image or a video. In this code, Object Detection is performed on the resized image using the MobileNetSSD model.

The first step is to preprocess the image and create a blob that can be fed as input to the model. This is done using the

`'cv2.dnn.blobFromImage()'` function, which resizes the image to 300x300 pixels, subtracts the mean RGB values, and scales the pixel values by a factor of **0.007843**.

The pre-processed image blob is then fed as input to the MobileNetSSD model using the `'net.setInput()'` function. The model performs a forward pass on the input image and generates a set of detections for the objects in the image.

The 'detections' array contains information about the detected objects, including their class ID, confidence score, and bounding box coordinates. The code loops through the detections using a for loop and checks if the confidence score for each detection is greater than 0.5. If the score is above the threshold, the code considers the detection as valid and proceeds to draw a rectangle and label around the detected object.

Finally, the code saves the detected objects and their respective coordinates in a list and returns the annotated image along with the list of detected objects as a response.

● Integrating.

Specify the paths to the prototxt and caffemodel files for the pre-trained MobileNetSSD model. The `'cv2.dnn.readNetFromCaffe()'` function is then used to read these files and load the model into memory. The 'net' object contains the loaded model, which we will use for object detection.

`img_resized = cv2.resize(img, (300, 300))`

resizes the input image 'img' to a width and height of 300 pixels, which is the input size required by the MobileNetSSD model. The resized image is stored in the 'img_resized' variable. `blob = cv2.dnn.blobFromImage(img_resized, 0.007843, (300, 300), (127.5, 127.5, 127.5), False)`

creates a blob from the resized image, which is used as input to the model for object detection. A blob is a multi-dimensional array that contains the image data in a format that can be used as input to a deep learning model. The `'cv2.dnn.blobFromImage()'` function takes the following arguments:

- `img_resized`: the resized image as a NumPy array.
- `scalefactor`: a scaling factor for the pixel values. Here, we set it to 0.007843 to scale the pixel values between 0 and 1.
- `size`: the size of the output blob. Here, we set it to (300, 300), which is the input size required by the MobileNetSSD model.
- `mean`: the mean value subtracted from each channel of the image. Here, we set it to (127.5, 127.5, 127.5) to normalize the pixel values.
- `swapRB`: a flag indicating whether to swap the R and B channels of the image. Here, we set it to False since OpenCV uses BGR order by default.

The resulting blob is stored in the blob variable, which we will use as input to the model for object detection.

'net.setInput(blob)' sets the input for the network to the preprocessed image blob.

detections = net.forward() runs the forward pass through the network and generates a set of detections for objects in the image.

'height, width, _ = img.shape' gets the height and width of the original image.

The code then loops through each detection in 'detections' using 'for i in range(detections.shape[2])'. For each detection, it checks if the confidence score is greater than 0.5 using 'conf = detections[0, 0, i, 2]'. If the confidence score is greater than 0.5, it extracts the class ID, class name, and coordinates of the detected object.

The coordinates are normalized values between 0 and 1, so the code multiplies them by the width and height of the original image to get the pixel coordinates.

'top_left' and 'bottom_right' are tuples representing the top left and bottom right coordinates of the bounding box around the detected object. The code draws a rectangle around the detected object using 'img = cv2.rectangle(img, top_left, bottom_right, (0, 200, 50), 3)', and adds the class name as a label using 'img = cv2.putText(img, class_name, (int(x1), int(y1) - 10), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 1, (200, 0, 50), 2, cv2.LINE_AA)'.
 The detected object's class name and coordinates are saved in a dictionary and appended to the 'detected_objects' list.

Finally, the annotated image is encoded in JPEG format using 'img_encoded = cv2.imencode('.jpg', img)[1]', and converted to bytes using 'img_bytes = img_encoded.tobytes()'. The response is a dictionary containing the base64-encoded image and the list of detected objects with their class names and coordinates.

Improved SSD for Object Detection

The Single Shot Detector (SSD) is a popular object detection algorithm that works by dividing an image into a grid of cells and predicting object bounding boxes and class probabilities for each cell. Here is a layer-by-layer explanation of the architecture of an SSD model:

Input Layer: The input to an SSD model is an image, which is passed through the input layer. The input layer typically has three channels for RGB images.

Convolutional Layers: The image is then processed by a series of convolutional layers. These layers extract features from the input image by convolving a set of learnable filters with the input image.

Feature Map Layers: The output of the convolutional layers is a set of feature maps, which represent different levels of abstraction of the input image. These feature maps are typically of different sizes and resolutions.

Prior Box Layers: Prior box layers generate a set of default bounding boxes at different locations and scales across the

feature maps. These boxes are used as a starting point for predicting object bounding boxes.

Convolutional Layers with Object Class Prediction Heads: Each feature map is then passed through a set of convolutional layers with object class prediction heads. These heads generate class probabilities for each default bounding box at each location and scale.

Output Layer: The final output of the SSD model is a set of predicted object bounding boxes and corresponding class probabilities.

Fig 1.

- o bounding boxes

Fig 2

Examples of predicted bounding boxes generated by the baseline model and our proposed model tested on the PASCAL visual object classes (VOC) dataset. Left column images (a, c, e, g, i, k, m, o) show the results of SSD (i.e., choosing the highest score proposal as the pseudoground truth). Right column images (b, d, f, h, j, l, n, p) show some bounding boxes produced by our method (i.e., applying EMBs). Applying EMB to SSD to detect objects yields better outcomes than the original SSD in almost all cases. However, as shown in (n), objects with similar colors and appearances are sometimes incorrectly predicted.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

To implement Machine Learning technology in this project, named Ad-Sol (solution for advertisement), is to implement the Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) algorithm for object detection in uploaded image files. The proposed solution aims to identify and localize objects within the uploaded images in real-time, without the need for a separate region proposal step. The SSD algorithm, which is a deep learning-based model, will be utilized to detect various objects in the images based on their object names.

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Fig 3.

Proof of Simplified Search with Implementation of SSD Image Processing

Fig 4.

VI. CONCLUSION

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A We know that advertising is the process of promoting a product, service, or idea to a target audience through various communication channels, such as print, radio, television, online media, billboards, and more. The purpose of advertising is to create awareness, generate interest, and persuade people to take a particular action, such as buying a product or service, signing up for a newsletter, visiting a website, or attending an event. Advertising is an essential aspect of marketing and plays a crucial role in the success of businesses and organizations.

Ad-Sol, provides several benefits to both advertisers and users. For advertisers, Ad-Sol offers a user-friendly platform to upload and manage their advertisements with a specified fee and duration. The application uses a machine learning algorithm, the Single Shot Detector, to detect objects in uploaded images and store the object names in a MySQL database to facilitate easy searching for users. Overall, Ad-Sol provides a user-friendly platform for advertising with the added benefit of object detection technology to enhance the user experience.

Fig 6.

Fig 7.

The generated result by the SSD algorithm, which is linked to the unique ID of images, is stored in the MySQL database and can be seen in Fig 7.

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